

ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF ENSURING INTER-ETHNIC HARMONY AND SOLIDARITY IN SOCIETY

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Abstract: The article examines the importance and future prospects of ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity in the society, its necessity, current issue, and in this process, its socio-philosophical, moral, spiritual, legal classification and specific features are analyzed.

Key words: society, interethnic harmony, solidarity, socio-philosophical, moral, spiritual, legal, future perspectives.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the context of increasing conflicts in the globalized world, including inter-ethnic conflicts, this problem is becoming especially important. In this regard, inter-ethnic harmony is becoming important as a decisive factor for any multi-ethnic state. The future of the country depends on the socio-spiritual activity, intelligence, morals, aesthetic, psychological and physical training of young people and their development in all aspects. It is known that the inner natural beauty of a person, having a comprehensively developed society and social life, a person's attitude to the world, being well-rounded in all aspects, his place in life, social orientation and self-awareness calling depends on the height of moral and aesthetic thinking.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

On the importance and historical-philosophical content of ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity in society, N. Jorayev, S. Safoyev, A. Jalilov, R. Jumayev, N. Mamanazarov, Q. Jorayev, R. Murtazayeva, R. Researchers such as Ubaidullayeva, I. Ergashev, H. Yunusova, V. Gentshke conducted scientific research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the years of independence, the maintenance of inter-civilian peace, stability and inter-ethnic harmony relations in our multi-ethnic republic is one of the great successes achieved in the development of Uzbekistan along its own path of development. Because in Uzbekistan, where representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples live, it is not easy to fundamentally renew the society, to transfer it from one state to another. Since the first days of independence in our country, ensuring interethnic harmony and stability has

been one of the main issues. At such a time, the state policy should be consistent and truthful.

The main principles of Uzbekistan's national policy are defined as:

- equal rights of all citizens of the republic, regardless of nationality, race, religious belief;
- Human rights, which determine the priority of the individual and social justice in society, are superior to all other rights;
- Pay attention to the rights of a small number of nationalities, respect their language, traditions and customs, preserve their uniqueness, and create the necessary conditions for their free and comprehensive development;
- Relying on a highly developed, socially oriented market economy that ensures social protection of every family and every person, regardless of nationality;
- Peaceful resolution of conflict situations in interethnic relations on a socio-political basis.

The idea of respecting human dignity, freedom of belief and dignity, and recognizing his rights and freedoms as the highest value is expressed in the comprehensive reforms being carried out in our country, and in the adopted laws and legal documents. In particular, it is noteworthy that the main goal and principle of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at ensuring the guarantees of the rights and freedoms of every citizen. The Constitution embodies the freedom of conscience and belief, ensures the equality of all nationalities and peoples living in our country, and is the main document that clearly demonstrates the independence of an independent country, the symbol of our happiness, the honor of our people, and the expression of our religious tolerance. After all, in each of its articles and clauses, both the norms of international law and the principles of national tolerance are reflected.

Uzbekistan's national policy model is also reflected in its activities in the field of foreign policy. Our republic actively participates in the process of developing principles on the issue of ensuring the rights of ethnic units in the international arena, implementing international agreements on the protection of the rights and freedoms of nations and peoples. In particular, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of Uzbekistan, the International Convention on the Elimination of All Types of Racial Discrimination, the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of Genocide Crimes, Nationality, Ethnicity, the fact that he signed a number of documents, such as the declaration

on the rights of persons belonging to a minority group in terms of religion or language, also determines the scope of actions in this direction.

This is the real reason why large-scale work is being carried out today in our country, especially in educational institutions, to raise the morale of young people, to strengthen the sense of national identity, and to carry out spiritual and moral reforms. Because today, the reforms that serve spiritual growth in our country are more important because they encourage the younger generation to be rightly proud of the memory of our great ancestors, to fight for peace, tranquility and prosperity, to appreciate independence and to live in honor of the Motherland. So, raising a generation that strives for perfection, mature and perfect in all respects is the most urgent task of today, and the leading force in the implementation of this task is the educational system. Therefore, education is the main condition and guarantee of human maturity and development of the nation.

Globalization processes in the world, especially the ministry, department and organizations responsible for youth education, parents, neighborhood activists, neighbors, teachers and trainers of educational institutions, and the public have a great responsibility. responsibility.

As long as there is regional instability, it is impossible to form an enlightened society. Because instability, regardless of its form, is created in different ways. Currently, ideological influence is spreading widely. From this point of view, educating a person who is independent and responsible for his actions, who knows his rights and freedoms, especially deciding the ideological beliefs of young people is one of the urgent issues of building an enlightened society. The complex social and international conflicts and global problems that we are witnessing make the issue of developing a system of correct views in the human relationship with the world, understanding the interdependence of all mankind acute. All the practices of socio-political reforms and changes, including the changes taking place in modern conditions, show that without changing the socio-political consciousness and people's thinking, it is impossible to achieve qualitative renewal of society.

Studying their general and private dialectics in the formation of worldviews makes it possible to take into account the priority of universal values. In our opinion, such an analysis is extremely important nowadays, when the socio-political situation in our republic requires the unification of all progressive social forces, groups, political parties, social movements, as well as nations, strata, social groups and society.

The development of information technologies in the world is becoming the most important factor affecting the formation and maturity of the young generation. Traditional mass media such as press, radio, television, telecommunications and wireless networks have been supplemented by modern means such as cellular communication, the Internet, satellite and cable television. Today's people get not only the information they need, but also behavioral stereotypes, values and ideals through mass media. Therefore, these tools have gone beyond their original purpose - information distribution and have become one of the factors of forming a person's worldview. Today, the worldview of young people is forming its own subculture, and it is significantly different from the worldview of the older generation. This can cause certain difficulties in the learning and communication process and even lead to misunderstanding.

CONCLUSION

Legal mechanisms for ensuring inter-ethnic harmony have been created in Uzbekistan, these mechanisms are working effectively and are constantly being improved. Representatives of all nationalities and peoples living in our country are living in national harmony and harmony, using the equal rights and broad opportunities stipulated in the Constitution and laws, making their due contribution to the development and prosperity of our country. Ensuring inter-ethnic harmony for all peoples and nationalities in our country is strengthened by our Constitution and current laws. Ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance relations in Uzbekistan, first of all, by preventing inter-religious conflicts, creates the basis for the formation of mutual cooperation, solidarity and solidarity between representatives of different religions.

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